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CITIZEN SCIENCE APPROACH FOR IMPROVEMENT OF SOIL HEALTH THROUGH SCHOOL COMPOSTING

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ABSTRACT

Soil quality is declining globally and requires urgent improvement through practical, widely accessible solutions. Composting has been used for millennia to enhance soil health, yet in urban areas, this sustainable, climate-friendly practice is often less accessible. Within this science project, the aim of the study was to integrate citizen science by involving students directly in the research process as a powerful way to engage schools, using composting as a hands-on method to connect education, sustainability, and community action.

In short term, the project aims to reduce organic waste sent to landfills, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and improve soil health, while simultaneously promoting science, environmental awareness, and community engagement. In the long term, the project seeks to influence policy makers to integrate circular economy practices city-wide and adapt school curricula to strengthen environmental education and science literacy.

The project involves three elementary schools in Novi Sad, and at least 45 student citizen scientists, who will maintain and monitor composting process at their school composters. It was decided that the following research methodology would be implemented to achieve the study objectives. Composting parameters, including temperature, pH, moisture, and EC, will be monitored using sensors, and the data will be recorded under the guidance of project team members and university mentors (two mentors per school). Subsequently, pot experiments will be conducted to assess the effects of compost addition on soil health and plant growth parameters. Physico-chemical and biological properties of compost and soil will be measured, including bacterial and fungal community analysis using 16S rRNA and ITS sequencing. The social aspect of the study will be

assessed regarding the impact of project participation on students' overall health and wellbeing, as well as on their knowledge and attitudes towards science and environmental issues, through questionnaires completed before and after participation.

To summarize, this citizen science approach connects education, sustainability, and policy, demonstrating how small-scale local actions can drive broader societal and environmental change.

Key words: citizen science, compost, education, sustainability, circular economy

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